

Enrolment Trends in Colleges of Education in Delta State: A Case Study of College of Education Warri

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ABSTRACT: The study dwelt on enrolment trends in Colleges of Education in Delta State, Nigeria with particular reference to College of Education, Warri. Enrolment of students were obtained for ten years in the approved course areas namely- School of Science, School of vocational studies, School of Arts & Social science, School of Basic Education (Early Childhood) and School of Languages. The study revealed a dwindling of enrolment in College of Education Warri. It was found that female students enrolled more in College of Education Warri and school wise, Early Childhood and Sciences are the least enrolled. Based on the finding, planning strategies were recommended such as- publicity should be made on the various courses offered in the college, encouragement be given to both genders to enroll in the various courses in terms of scholarship should be granted to students to study in areas lagging behind in enrolment. Good management practices like early release of result of graduates was also recommended.

KEYWORDS: Colleges of Education, Enrolment, Trends, College of Education.

INTRODUCTION

Education as a discipline is the mother of all disciplines. The uniqueness is that education produces teachers of all calibers for all disciplines. No wonder the National Policy on Education asserted that “No Nation can rise above the quality of its teachers” (FRN, 2004). The basic of teacher production is the Colleges of Education in Nigeria sequel to the scrapping of Teacher Training Colleges that produce TC II products. Any education product is a professional and is qualified to teach in schools. Colleges of Education are tertiary institutions all over the world that produce teachers for elementary and primary schools. They are middle power human resource in whom national development is hinged upon.

Colleges of Education are staffed with calibers of teaching ranging from masters to doctorate degree holders. These no doubt are deemed capable hand to impart requisite knowledge to the students. Grandaunts of Colleges of Education possess the Nigerian Certificate of Education (NCE). The curriculum of College of Education is planned with various learning experiences that will cater for the teaching of primary education (Atakpo, 2020). The institutions are accredited from time to time to ensure that minimum standards are maintained all over the country and the NCE recipient are at par with their counterpart all over Nigeria.

The role of Colleges of Education in Educational Development of the Nation

Colleges of Education produce teachers for primary school education. By implication, the primary school level is dependent on the grandaunts from the Colleges of Education who become teachers in the schools. The NCE teachers produced in Colleges of Education are veritable agents for laying solid foundation for the educational development of any nation. This is because elementary education in pre-primary and primary education levels is the basis of education upon which other levels are laid. The NCE teachers are professionally trained teachers to master the rudiment of teaching in basic education. Gone are the days when any one teaches without the pedagogical knowledge. Such teachers are quacks and are not professionals (Atakpo, 2024) and the NCE teachers have come to rescue the primary school education from unprofessional teachers. They are source of supply of students to universities. Apart from secondary school products who go through University Matriculation Examination to read a four-year course, NCE graduates are admitted to read three-year courses. Presently in Nigeria and Delta State in particular, there is dearth of teachers in the primary schools arising from a good number of teachers who have retired as well as non-employment of new ones to replace the needed manpower in the primary school system. The area of specialization of these teachers ranges from the Sciences, Social Science, Vocational and Arts. The grandaunts of Colleges of Education are therefore repository of knowledge needed for grooming the primary school pupils towards national development. For instance, science students in Colleges of Education are those persons who enrolled to read mathematics, Chemistry, Physics, Health and Physical Education. The role of these teachers in developing the science base of pupils cannot be overemphasized.

The knowledge of science that children have depend to an extent on what they are taught in school. Many learners dislike mathematics even at primary school level. This can be attributed to poor subject mastery as well as inadequate teachers in the schools (Atakpo, 2024). Uzoma (2017) found that enrolment in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria is fluctuating in respect of mathematics. On gender analysis, Uzoma study revealed that a wide gap between male and female students' enrolment in all the academic sessions studied, with male students taking the lead.

The need for Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) teachers arose out of the desire to produce quality teachers for the teeming primary pupils' population in Nigeria. In the 1980s there was a surge in demand for NCE. The reason being that NCE teachers are next to degree teachers as higher education products. Those who could not afford degree education opted for Colleges of Education to satisfy their quest for tertiary education. Moreover, there was no marked difference between NCE teachers and university education teachers as all of them went for the National Youth Service Corp. The colleges were bubbling with life in the past. Students who particularly want to teach in primary schools normally enrol in Colleges of Education. The crop of Colleges of Education students were hard working and dedicated students who upon graduating could teach in even in secondary school at class 4 or 5 levels talk less of primary school level. The preparatory period is three years after which the recipient bag Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE). Colleges of Education are to produce top-class teachers who are highly motivated and fully prepared for teaching at the basic education level. They are also for producing professionals with world class quality personnel imbued with discipline, integrity and competence for expanding the basic education (Federal Republic of Nigeria 2019).

The body responsible for prescribing curriculum content of Colleges of Education is the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE). She institutes quality assurance by monitoring and accreditation of courses periodically. The graduates from Colleges of Education are therefore competent to teach in any primary schools in Nigeria. The NCE certificate is strengthened with TRCN which lays more credence to its certificate.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014:43) outlined the objectives of Teacher Education as to:

- a) Produce highly motivated conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of the educational system;
- b) Further encourage the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers;
- c) Help teachers fit into the social life of the community and the society at large and enhance their commitment to national goals;
- d) Provide teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and to make them adaptable to changing situation and e. Enhance teachers' commitment to the teaching profession.

Evolution of Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

In Nigeria, the evolution of Colleges of Education started with the Ashby Commission report of 1960 that recommended manpower need of different sector of the economy. The education report was captioned "Investment in Education". The report saw the need to set up teacher training institution for the nascent education system after the independence. Teacher education has been on transformational stages since the Ashy Report of 1960. The Federal and Regional government in Nigeria established five teacher training institutions known as "Advanced Teachers Training Colleges" in 1962. These institutions functioned as teacher producers and later metamorphosed into Colleges of Education with additional ones established in many states of the federation. The Advanced Teachers Training Colleges included- Lagos, Ibadan and Zaria, Owerri, Kano and Abraka and others between 1962 to 1968. These institutions were latter converted to Colleges of Education. The National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) was instituted by Decree 3 of 1989 as the statutory body that regulates the programmes and activities carried out by Colleges of Education in Nigeria. NCCE has the statutory responsibility of- (i) Lay down minimum standards for all programmes of teacher education and accredit their certificates and other academic awards, (ii) Approve guidelines setting out criteria for accreditation of all Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Section 5 (c) and (d) Decree 13 of 17 of 1989 that set up the Commission. This has been amended to be Act 12 of 1993 and has the responsibility of - (a) Lay down minimum standards for all programmes of teacher education and accredit their certificates and other academic awards, (b) Approve guidelines setting out criteria for accreditation of all Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Colleges of education can be said to have a foundation statement judging from the responsibilities of NCCE.

Brief History of College of Education, Warri.

What is known as College of Education Warri was Advanced Teacher College, Ihogbe in Benin city, Bendel state (now Edo State) that was established in 1979. It metamorphosed from Advanced Teacher College to College of Education in 1980 and was commissioned by the Executive Governor of the defunct Bendel State in the of person of His Excellency, Late Chief (Professor) Ambrose Ali and was transferred to Warri, then Bendel State and now Delta State in 1981. It first occupied a temporary site that shared a common boundary with Hussey College, Warri, Nigeria. She has since moved to its permanent site. College of Education, Warri, produces manpower for primary and basic schools in Nigeria. The college in her mission statement enumerated the following- Production of personnel who are well-motivated, professionally discipline and of integrity and competence; producing a crop of teachers who are competence in research, guidance and counselling as well as curriculum planning, development and delivery;

production of teachers who can impart knowledge, attitudes and skills with unfolding ICT apart from conventional teaching strategies; and teachers who are constructive change agents socio-economically, morally and spiritually through continuous preparation and upgrading of teachers with professionally competence who can stand out with a sense of social responsibility and commitment. The following provost have served the college from her inception till date.

Table I: List of Provost of College Education Warri till date.

S/N	NAME	YEARS SERVED
1	Dr. H.S.A. Aluyi	1979 – 1989
2	Mr. P. Ifeta (Acting	1993 – 1995
3	Prof E. N. Emenanjo	1990 – 1993
4	Prof A. C. Unomah	1995 – 2002
5	Dr. Felix Omojevbe Money (Acting)	2002
6	Prof Igho Joe	2002 – 2009
7	Dr. Sylvester SeleEbisine (Acting)	2009 – 2016
8	Prof (Mrs) Mary OlireEdema	2016 - 2021
	Dr. D. O. Oyovwe	2021- till date

Source : https://coewarri.edu.ng/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/ACADEMIC_BRIEF.pdf. Academic Brief

Roles of Colleges of Education for National development

The place of Colleges of Education for national development is significant. Colleges of Education are saddled with responsibilities of producing middle manpower human resource for Basic education. Colleges of Education would facilitate easy achievement of the national goal by producing teachers with highly personal and professional discipline, integrity and dedicated teachers with appropriate skills and intellectual depth (Oladimeji, Adeyanju & Fakorede, 2017). Colleges of Education are to conduct courses in education for qualified teachers apart from provide full-time courses in teaching, instruction and training (Ebisine, 2014). College of Education is the foundation of education development of any nation. That is to say without Colleges of Education products, no proper foundations for all crops of professions would have been possible. Thus, NCE teachers laid the foundations for lawyers, medical doctors, teachers, engineers, the military personnel and others. Colleges of Education have alleviated the manpower problems of the nation over the years through the production of a large number of non-graduate professional (NCE) teachers that teach in our primary and junior secondary schools (Oga & Okpaga, n.d, and Ekeng & Oritsebemigho, 2014). Atanda and Adeniran (2020) gave the following as relevance of Colleges of Education:

1. To develop adolescent minds for national development;
2. Teacher professionalism improvement
3. For improvement in Basic Education standard in Nigeria;
4. Youth improvement in technical and science education for the nation;
5. It gives room for direct admission of NCE graduates into universities for further studies leading to acquisition of Bachelor of Education Degree, with other areas of specialization;
6. Avenue for continuing education for people that are working through the Colleges' Sandwich Programmes;
7. Colleges of education serve as action that support for UNESCO aspirations like Education for All (EFA), Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), etc.

Trends on Enrolment in Teacher Education

It is recognized that Colleges of Education are teacher education institutions which produce teachers for elementary education globally. However, there are insinuations from various researchers on down ward trend in enrolment in education programmes worldwide. Oladeji lamented shortage of skilled teachers which has led to had low enrolment and poor student's academic performance. This is an indication that may be due to low enrolment in tertiary institution to study the course. Momoh, Abudu, Ukachi and Luqman (2020) study show that the percentage of female enrolment between 2010/2011 and 2014/2015 academic sessions was less than 40%. This implies relatively low female enrolment in polytechnic education vis-à-vis their male counterpart. Ethe and Odjegba (2018) lamented that enrolment into Colleges of Education in Nigeria has dwindled down and the interest in College of Education among students has also gone down below the bet. Our children are losing interest in College of Education. This is not good for the development of education in the country. Aina and Ayodele (2018) equally laments poor enrolment of female students in colleges of education. Admission and placement in education programmes is not as rigorous as it is in other programs like engineering, law because of usual shortage of applicants seeking admission into programs that would prepare them as teachers in universities and colleges (Ogunyinka, Okeke & Adedoyin, 2015). Aina and Ayodele (2018) lamented that financial purposes have

made the institutions to run different academic programmes that are of no benefit to the students. On the contrary, Akporehe and Nkedishu (2020) and Twaddle, EdD and Tamarah Smith (2023) studies on perception of self-efficacy factors to teaching by pre-service teachers was high. Ugwo, Yusuf and Oyedoyin (2024) reported a low enrolment for sciences which was attributed to challenges in student enrolment from the study carried out with Federal College of Education, Okene, Nigeria. In the area of early child hood education, Ajayi (2008) conducted a study which found out that of the numerous universities in the South West, only 10 of them were offering ECE and that the number of enrolees were very low at undergraduate and Postgraduate levels. Shinco (2020) lamented that most ECE schools employ unqualified teachers such as secondary school dropouts, holders of Teachers Grade II certificate. This no doubt shows dearth of ECE teachers in Sokoto State which was the area of study. In 2022, out of the 469,125 slots allotted Colleges of Education, only 35,466 or 7.56 per cent were admitted, while in 2023, out of 472,200 quota, only 11,735 enrolled in Colleges of Education, thus representing 2.49 percent enrolees (Vanguard News Paper 2024). This revelation is definitely the source of low enrolment in College of Education, Warri, Nigeria, and in all the schools.

Research Questions

1. What is the overall admission in College of Education, Warri, for the last ten years?
2. What is the trend in admission for male and female students in College of Education, Warri for the last ten years?
3. What is the admission trend for the 5 schools for the last ten years?

METHODOLOGY

The study is expose-facto research deign that used a self-constructed inventory checklist, titled “Enrolment in College of Education, Warri (ECEW) to collect data from the records of admission unit in College of Education, Warri. The records of ten years were obtained from the school for the study. The instrument was validated by the two experts in the Department of Educational Management and Foundations, Delta State university, Abraka. Their inputs were used to improve on the instrument. The data were collected according to years, schools and gender for the ten years. Data were transformed to percentages and analysed in histograms for the various years.

The purpose of the study was to determine the trend of enrolment in College of Education, Warri; find out enrolment by gender and by schools namely Science; Vocational & Technical Education; Art & Social Science; Basic Education (Early Child) and Languages.

Table 1: Data collected from College of Education, Warri

Female	SCHOOLS															Grand Total
	SCIENCES			Arts & Social science			Vocational & Technical Education			Basic Education (Early Childhood			Languages			
	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	
2013/2014	83	106	189	111	147	258	82	98	180	3	33	36	53	94	147	810
2014/2015	44	97	141	41	142	183	26	105	131	2	30	32	19	63	82	569
2015/2016	30	61	91	29	102	131	16	79	95	2	13	15	12	48	60	392
2016/2017	36	48	84	44	98	142	25	80	105	2	29	31	17	46	63	425
2017/2018	31	65	96	46	106	152	15	82	97	2	40	42	13	76	89	476
2018/2019	28	56	84	26	78	103	12	70	82	2	16	18	8	55	63	350
2019/2020	32	51	83	36	76	112	20	62	82	4	35	39	10	53	63	379
2020/2021	15	37	52	21	70	91	13	47	60	-	18	18	16	34	50	271
2021/2022	18	22	40	20	53	73	13	45	58	3	13	16	14	31	45	232

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2022/2023	20	28	48	12	56	68	13	35	48	-	4	4	25	64	89	257
TOTAL	337	571	908	386	928	1314	235	703	938	20	231	251	187	564	751	4161

Table 2: Data transformed into percentages

Female	SCHOOLS															Grand Total
	Sciences			Arts & Social science			Vocational & Technical Education			Basic Education (Early Childhood)			Languages			
	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	M	F	Total	
2013/2014	83(43.9%)	106(56.1%)	189100%	111(43%)	147(57%)	258100%	82(45.6%)	98(54.4%)	180100%	3(8.3%)	33(91.7%)	36100%	53(36%)	94(64%)	147100%	810
2014/2015	44(31.2%)	97(68.8%)	141100%	41(22.4%)	142(77.6%)	183100%	26(19.8%)	105(80.2%)	131100%	2(6.3%)	30(93.7%)	32100%	19(23.2%)	63(76.8%)	82100%	569
2015/2016	30(33%)	61(67%)	91100%	29(22.1%)	102(77.9%)	131100%	16(16.8%)	79(83.2%)	95100%	2(13.3%)	13(86.7%)	15100%	12(20%)	48(80%)	60100%	392
2016/2017	36(42.9%)	48(57.1%)	84100%	44(30.9%)	98(69.1%)	142100%	25(23.8%)	80(76.2%)	105100%	2(6.5%)	29(93.5%)	31100%	17(27%)	46(73%)	63100%	425
2017/2018	31(32.3%)	65(67.7%)	96100%	46(30.3%)	106(69.7%)	152100%	15(15.5%)	82(84.5%)	97100%	2(4.8%)	40(95.2%)	42100%	13(14.6%)	76(85.4%)	89100%	476
2018/2019	28(33.3%)	56(66.7%)	84100%	26(25.2%)	78(74.8%)	103100%	12(14.6%)	70(85.4%)	82100%	2(11.1%)	16(88.9%)	18100%	8(12.7%)	55(87.3%)	63100%	350
2019/2020	32(38.6%)	51(61.4%)	83100%	36(32.1%)	76(67.9%)	112100%	20(24.4%)	62(75.6%)	82100%	4(10.3%)	35(89.7%)	39100%	10(15.9%)	53(84.1%)	63100%	379
2020/2021	15(28.8%)	37(71.2%)	52100%	21(23.1%)	70(76.9%)	91100%	13(21.7%)	47(78.3%)	60100%	-0%	18(100%)	18100%	16(32%)	34(68%)	50100%	271
2021/2022	18(45%)	22(55%)	40100%	20(27.4%)	53(72.6%)	73100%	13(22.4%)	45(77.6%)	58100%	3(18.8%)	13(81.2%)	16100%	14(31.1%)	31(68.9%)	45100%	232
2022/2023	20(41.7%)	28(58.3%)	48100%	12(17.6%)	56(82.4%)	68100%	13(27.1%)	35(72.9%)	48100%	-0%	4(100%)	4100%	25(28.1%)	64(71.9%)	89(100%)	257
TOTAL	337	571	908	386	928	1313	235	703	938	20	231	251	187	564	751	4161

Research Question 1: What is the overall enrolment in College of Education, Warri, for the ten years?

Table 3: Distribution of students' enrolment for the period of study which is ten years

SN	YEAR`	ENROLMENT
1	2013/2014	810
2	2014/2015	569
3	2015/2016	392
4	2016/2017	425
5	2017/2018	476
6	2018/2019	350
7	2019/2020	379
8	2020/2021	271
9	2021/2022	232
10	2022/2023	257
	TOTAL	4661

Table 3 showed that a total of 4161 students were enrolled into the institution for the period of study. The distribution of students' enrolment for each year are equally indicated. The data showed that there was a great difference in enrolment from 2013/2014 and 2022/2023 academic sessions (810-257).

Research Question 2: What is the trend in admission for male and female students in College of Education, Warri for the ten years?

Table 4: Admission trend for male and female students in College of Education, Warri, for the ten years.

Year	Male	Female	Total
2013/2014	332 (100%)	478 (100%)	810
2014/2015	132 (40%)	437 (94%)	569
2015/2016	89 (27%)	303 (63%)	392
2016/2017	124 (37%)	301 (63%)	425
2017/2018	107 (32%)	369 (77%)	476
2018/2019	76 (22%)	274 (57%)	350
2019/2020	102 (31%)	277 (58%)	379
2020/2021	65 (20%)	206 (43%)	271
2021/2022	70 (21%)	162 (34%)	232
2022/2023	70 (21%)	187 (39%)	257
Total	1167	2994	4161

Table 4 shows a dwindling trend in enrolment considering 810 students in 2023/2024 to 257 in 2023/2024 academic sessions. On yearly basis, there is an undulating trend in enrolment that is reducing for many successive years with a few years exceptional. The male students' enrolment for the 10 years was 1167, while female students' enrolment was 2994. There was a sharp decline in students' enrolment from 2013/2024 to 2022/2023 sessions. The male students' enrolment trend was as follow- 100%, 40%, 27%, 37%, 32%, 22%, 31%, 20%, 21%, 21%. Female students' enrolment trend was as follow- 100%, 94%, 63%, 63%, 77%, 57%, 58%, 43%, 34%, 39%.

Using this formula, $\Delta\% = ((B - A) / A) \times 100$

$\Delta\%$ =Percentage change

A = Base Year

B = Current Year value

C = Number of Years

257- 810/ 810 x 100 = - 68%. There is a negative trend of -68% in students' enrolment in College of Education, Warri, Delta State, for the period of study. By implication only 32% of students who enrolled in 2013/2014 enrolled for the period of study.

Research Question 3: What is the admission trend for each of the five (5) schools for the 10 years.

From Table 2, using this using this formula, $\Delta\% = ((B - A) / A) \times 100$, where

$\Delta\%$ =Percentage change

A = Base Year

B = Current Year value

C = Number of Years

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School of Sciences= $48-189/189 \times 100 = -75\%$
 School of Art and Social Science= $68-258/258 \times 100 = -74\%$
 School of Vocational and Technical Education= $48-180/180 \times 100 = -73\%$
 School of Early Childhood Education= $4-36/36 \times 100 = -89\%$
 School of Language Art= $89-148/147 \times 100 = -40\%$

From the analysis above, school of Early Childhood Education is the worst hit in students' enrolment. The school that is least affected in enrolment is school of Language Art. School of Early Childhood Education had -83% enrolment trend. This means that only 17% of the base year enrolment was achieved. In school of Science, enrolment was -75%. By implication, only 25% of the base year was the enrolment for the period of study. School Art and Social Science had -74% enrolment. By this, only 26% of students enrolled considering the base year. School of Vocational and Technical education had -73%. By implication, only 27 enrolment was achieved compared with the base year. School of Language Art had -40%. This means that the school had 60% enrolment in relation with the base year.

The figures below further explain the enrolment trends in the years studied for male and female students and for the different schools.

Figure: i

Figure: ii

Figure : iii

Figure: iv

Figure: v

Figure: vi

Figure: vii

Figure: viii

Figure: ix

Figure: x

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings in research question one showed that there is a dwindling of enrolment in College of Education, Warri, for the period of study- 2013/2014 to 2022/2023 academic sessions. The finding is in agreement with Will (2023) which revealed that between 2008 and 2020, the number of education students declined by about a quarter of a million. Aragon (2016) finding in ACT and the Department of Education of the US also showed fewer high school graduates are interested in pursuing education majors and fewer college students are pursuing teaching careers. The finding is further supported by Ethe and Odjegba (2018) who equally lamented that enrolment into Colleges of Education in Nigeria has dwindled down and the interest in College of Education among students has also gone down below the bet. The reason could be a result of harsh economic situation of the state, preferences for degree education course and low self-efficacy and interest of young people on teaching profession which many say is not high paying and attractive. Khan, Shiraz, Shah and Muzamil (2023) had also attributed low registration in sciences education to factors ranging from students individual and interpersonal factors to institutional factors. Uzoma (2017) also found that enrolment in mathematics is low, with male students taking the lead in enrolment.

Research Question two finding showed that male students enrol less than female students in all the years observed in College of Education, Warri. This finding however contradicts Aina and Ayodele (2018) who found poor enrolment of female students in Colleges of Education. Uzoma (2017) also found male students taking the lead in enrolment than female students.

Findings of research question three showed that School of Basic/Early Childhood Education (ECE) had the lowest enrolment for the period of study as enrolment went as low as- 89% (only about 11% of enrolment) of the base year. That School

of Early Childhood Education (ECE) was the lowest in enrolment, aligns with Ajayi (2008) who found out that only few institutions offer ECE course and that the students' enrolment is relatively low in number. The Ajayi finding is supported by Shinco (2020) who lamented the dearth of qualified ECE teachers in Sokoto State which invariably would arise from low enrolment in Colleges of Education in Sokoto State. School of Science went as low as- 74% (26% enrolment) of the base year. This was followed by school of Art and Social Science, School of Vocational and Technical education and School of Language Art. The findings of low enrolment in science aligns with Ugwo, Yusuf and Oyedoyin (2024) and Owolabi, Dansu and Onofowokan (2013) who had made same observations in their studies. The vanguard (2024) finding from Joint Admission Matriculation of low enrollees in Colleges of Education also account for the reason of low enrolment in College of Education, Warri, and in all the schools.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that enrolment of students into College of Education, Warri, is dwindling. Female students enrolled more than male student. Early Childhood Education are almost on extinction from the institution. Enrolment in school of Science, Art and Social Science, Vocational and Technical Education and Language Art are very low.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Drive should be made for more students to enrol in the institution;
2. Male students should be encouraged to enrol in the institution.
3. All the schools (Courses) should be advocated for so that students would enrol in them.
4. More researches should be carried on causes of low enrolment in Colleges of Education .

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